

Notes on software quality

Supplement to “Base4NFDI service integration procedures”
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Authors

Aleksandra Grudskaia (0009-0005-2652-3330)
Raphael Ritz (0000-0003-4615-6804)
Christian Schäfer-Neth (0000-0002-6995-8706)

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Overview

To ensure high software quality, the service teams are asked to go through a procedure of self-assessment three times, two of which are during the Integration Phase: at the time of application for the Ramp-Up Phase after about 18 months and at the end of the Integration Phase. To guide the service teams, TA2 provides a check list of relevant quality criteria the service teams are asked to fill in. Details can be found in the tables given below.

Base4NFDI agreed on 8 categories of software quality criteria:

1. Accessibility & Availability
2. Attractiveness
3. Confidentiality & Safety
4. Documentation
5. Fault tolerance

6. Modifiability & Maintainability
7. Performance
8. Testability

Within these categories, different criteria are relevant depending on the user context - cf. list below. In Base4NFDI, we consider 3 user groups:

1. Developers
2. System administrators
3. End users - scientists

Supported by TA2, the teams themselves should assess which of the criteria listed below apply to their service and whether the service or software fulfils the criteria. This self-assessment should take place three times:

1. Application for the Ramp-Up Phase
2. End of Integration Phase
3. End of Ramp-Up Phase

Criteria by category and phase

Below we list all the criteria in tables. In each row we list a criterion and indicate whether it should be met in **step I** (application for Ramp-Up Phase), **step II** (end of Integration Phase), or **step III** (end of Ramp-Up Phase). Not all criteria must be met at the very first step, and not all of the criteria are mandatory even at the Ramp-Up Phase - it depends on the service. Therefore, an **exclamation mark in the last column** indicates that the criterion is mandatory in step III, and a **double exclamation mark** indicates that the criterion is mandatory in every step. Ideally, after every round of self-assessment, the set of fulfilled requirements should include the set in the respective column (I, II or III).

Some of the criteria might be not applicable at all for some of the services and there might be exceptions: a check point might be not applicable to the specific service. If this is the case, it should be briefly explained.

Accessibility & Availability

Accessibility is the degree to which a product or system can be used by people with the widest range of diversity and capabilities to achieve a specified goal in a concrete context of use. **Availability** is the degree to which a system, product, or component is operational and accessible when required for use.

	I	II	III	
For the Developer:				
The source code should be written using one of the common modern tools and saved in a readable and openable format.	X	X	X	!!
The libraries used in the source code should be always available and have long-term support.	X	X	X	!!
For the End User:				
The service can be installed on the user's PC or accessed from it regardless of the version of the OS and the type of the hardware (for all reasonably modern hardware types and OS).	X	X	X	!
The service also can be installed to/accessed from the smartphone/tablet, especially if using mobile devices with this product has advantages over using laptops/stationary computers.			X	
The process of getting an account with the whole functionality should be simple and straightforward, without too much waiting time, ideally it should be automated.			X	!
The service can be used both online and offline, with later synchronisation, if needed.			X	!
The user should be able to access the service at any time they need; in case a maintenance is needed, it should be announced well in advance.	X	X	X	!
The situations when the user can not get the access to the service because of the absence of a responsible person (for the first time or later) should be avoided - all the processes ideally should be automated.			X	!
The user should be able to adjust font size and, ideally, it should be possible to use the product together with extensions for blind users.	X	X	X	
The user should be able to easily access all account information, such as email, user name, account expiration date, and contact details for the prolongation of the account, also disk space usage, number of files and their size, connected users and all other relevant information.			X	!
The server can remember the user's account details to keep them logged in.			X	
The server should be available from abroad without a VPN (unless this security measure is necessary).			X	

The user should be able to decide whether they want to use the server with or without 2FA (unless this security measure is necessary and 2FA must be mandatory).			X	
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Attractiveness

Attractiveness is the degree to which a user interface enables pleasing and satisfying interaction, including topics like internationalisation and localisation.

	I	II	III	
For the Developer:				
The source code should be written following the same style.	X	X	X	!!
For the End User:				
The colors used in the product should go together well and should be taken from existing color schemes. The colors in the color scheme should be distinguishable in grey shadows.	X	X	X	
The interface should be intuitive - no confusing signs and/or colors.			X	!
The interface should be intuitive - easy to understand if buttons are clickable or not, if boxes are ticked or not.			X	!
There should be day/night mode switcher, ideally taken from the device settings.			X	
The interface language should be understandable by all users (minimum requirements: German and English).	X	X	X	!
Time and currency is shown in local format.			X	

Confidentiality & Safety

Confidentiality is the degree to which a product or system ensures that data are accessible only to those who have been authorised access. **Safety** is the degree to which a product or system mitigates the potential personal risk to humans or to system components, in the intended contexts of use.

	I	II	III	
For the Developer:				
In the source code, the system of user categories and the rights of each category should be understandable (documented and explained).	X	X	X	!!

For the End User:				
The user categories and the rights of the users should be understandable.			X	
Different levels of privacy of the data should exist (if applicable) and should be understandable which users have which rights.	X	X	X	
If the data contains viruses or is potentially dangerous, automated checks should reveal this and issue a warning that someone else is getting access to the data.	X	X	X	!
The admins/users with higher privileges can not access other users' private data. In general, no one can access private files or data of another user.	X	X	X	!
If the data is not open for a user, this user can not get access to it in any way.	X	X	X	!
The system of user privileges should be self-consistent.	X	X	X	!!

Documentation

	I	II	III	
For the Developer:				
The source code should be documented.	X	X	X	!!
All the variables, structures, classes should be explained.	X	X	X	!!
All functions should have verbal description / comments with references if needed.	X	X	X	!!
For the Admin:				
There should be step-by-step instructions for the installation process and list of dependencies. Alternatively, a makefile could be provided together with the software.			X	!
For the End User:				
For the console application -h and --help should work and show the appropriate documentation.	X	X	X	!
In case of graphical interface - online or in-built - up-to-date documentation with all the features and possible use of the software should be available.	X	X	X	!
Significant updates of the software should be highlighted in the documentation.			X	!

The documentation can be downloaded as a single file.			X	
The examples of use should be in the documentation.			X	
The documentation should be version controlled.	X	X	X	!!
In addition to documentation, there should be a support team for solving unforeseen problems.			X	!
There should be FAQ in addition to documentation. (As an option, in-built AI bot in case of unavailability of the support team)			X	!

Fault tolerance

Fault tolerance is the degree to which a system, product, or component operates as intended despite the presence of hardware or software faults.

	I	II	III	
For the End User:				
All changes should be autosaved regularly - in case of a sudden hardware/software failure, the changes should not be lost.	X	X	X	!
'Silent failures' (without informative error messages) should never appear; the error messages should help users.	X	X	X	!!
No need to re-login or re-open the server in case of shortly losing of connection - the server work should be stable even in case of unstable internet.	X	X	X	!

Modifiability & Maintainability

Modifiability is the degree to which a product or system can be effectively and efficiently modified without introducing defects or degrading the product. **Maintainability** is the degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified by the intended maintainers.

	I	II	III	
For the Developer:				
Each function in the source code should be responsible for one task.	X	X	X	!!
The dependencies used in the source code should be always available and have long-term support.	X	X	X	!!
There should be a clear list of dependencies.	X	X	X	!!

All changes should be version controlled.	X	X	X	!!
Commits should be done regularly with properly made commit messages.	X	X	X	!!
For the End User:				
Old functionality should not disappear without leaving a trace. New functionality appears in addition to the old one.			X	!

Performance

Performance is how well the system works taking into account the amount of resources used under stated conditions.

	I	II	III	
For the Developer:				
In case of non-obvious (or better any) parallelisation there should be justification why it is needed and why it is done in this way.			X	!
Parallelisation should be flexible and adjustable to the hardware used.			X	!
If something can be done more efficiently, it should be done in this way.	X	X	X	!
The resources should not be wasted - the allocated memory should be used properly.	X	X	X	!!
For the End User:				
For a simple 'hello world' case, the software should work on any relatively modern machine.	X	X	X	!!
The user can decide how many of the available resources they want to use.	X	X	X	!
The way how to change the use of the resources should be described in the documentation, some examples also should be there.	X	X	X	!

Testability

Testability is the degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which test criteria can be established for a system, product, or component [1]. It is connected strongly to modifiability.

	I	II	III	
For the Developer:				
All the functions should be tested and the tests should be robust.	X	X	X	!!
When a new version of the software is issued, old tests, after modification should show the same results.	X	X	X	!
The tests should be automated and permanent.	X	X	X	!!
Tests should fully cover the source code.	X	X	X	!
Tests should be realistic.	X	X	X	!!
Tests should be documented or can be run as a script.	X	X	X	!
For the End User:				
If applicable, there should be a test data set, with the known output, so that the user understands if everything is installed correctly and works as it should.	X	X	X	!